

Food and lifestyle impact on breath VOCs using portable mass spectrometer – pilot study across European countries

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Abstract

In the modern world, many people are changing old dietary and lifestyle habits to improve the quality of their living – to treat or just prevent possible diseases. The main goal of this pilot study was to assess the food and lifestyle impact on exhaled breath VOCs in various population groups. It was done by employing a recently validated portable membrane-inlet mass spectrometer – MIMS. Thus, the obtained results would also represent the additional confirmation for the employment of the new instrument in the breath analysis. The pilot study involved 151 participants across Europe, including people with overweight, obesity, type 2 diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular disease, people with poor-quality diet and professional athletes. Exhaled breath acetone, ethanol, isoprene, and n-pentane levels were determined in samples before the meal, and 120 min after the meal. Obtained basal ppb_v values were mainly in accordance with previously reported, which confirms that MIMS instrument can be used in the breath analysis. Combining the quantified levels along with the information about the participants' lifestyle habits collected via questionnaire, an assessment of the food and lifestyle impact was obtained. Notable alteration in examined VOC levels upon meal consumption was detected in more than 70 % of all participants, with exception for isoprene, which was affected in about half of participants. Lifestyle parameters impact was examined using ANOVA on ranks test. Statistically significant differences in basal breath VOC levels were observed among all examined population groups. Also, n-pentane and ethanol levels significantly differed in people of different ages, as well as acetone levels in people with different physical activity habits. These findings are promising for further, more focused research using MIMS technique in breath analysis.

Keywords:

Food, Lifestyle, Exhaled breath, VOCs, MIMS

Introduction

In modern times we are facing and discovering numerous disorders, syndromes, intolerances, allergies, and diseases that are food related [1]. Among all, the greatest concern in all societies is metabolic disorders, due to their prevalence worldwide [2, 3]. As the expression “metabolic disorder” is vague itself, it can be concluded that there is no single exact cause of these conditions and that consequences and symptoms are not always the same. However, malnutrition and lack of physical activity in modern humanity are certainly significant contributors to disorders [4, 5]. Such type of lifestyle causes overweight, which can later lead to obesity, type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), and cardiovascular diseases (CVD) [2, 6, 7]. Above all, this process is not always straightforward, and each of these disorders can lead to another and so forth.

A lot of research is required for revealing disorders’ relationship to diet and food metabolism. To provide accurate diagnosis and optimal therapy or diet recommendation, a personalized approach is needed [8]. This is because lifestyle habits and living environment strongly contribute to our metabolism, in addition to our genetics and constitution [9]. Until the breakthrough of information technology, this was done in nutritional offices only. However, such an approach can be time and money-consuming. More importantly, it is almost impossible to enable a widespread application with conventional approaches and rely just on medical systems. These days, numerous mobile applications are based on observation of users’ habits, and they make conclusions and recommendations using big data analysis [10]. However, to obtain accurate insight into the person’s condition, some biochemical parameters need to be checked. Conventionally, it is done by blood analysis, which is invasive and not comfortable for all people. Moreover, it is time-consuming and requires a couple of visits to different medical specialists to obtain results. Although the best approach, it cannot be used for rapid screening of a large number of people.

The good thing is that there is an alternative to blood analysis, which has great potential to be used as a screening diagnostic in the future [11]. Namely, some metabolites in our body are volatile and they tend to pass the blood: air barrier in the lungs and reach human breath during exhalation [12, 13]. In that way, it is possible to have an instant reflection of the state of the organism by analyzing the exhaled breath [14, 15, 16]. As a matter of fact, the diagnostic potential of breath analysis has been known for a long time [17] and it is already used in some nutritional diagnostics, such as the detection of lactose intolerance [18]. Breath sampling is non-invasive and does not require sample preparation [19], which makes it suitable for wide applications.

As with every technique, there are several limitations in breath analysis. It is very unstable and requires very careful sampling and analysis as various interfering endogenous and exogenous factors exist [19]. Additionally, breath analysis lacks standardization [20] which is why scientists in the field are putting a lot of effort to establish solid protocols [21, 22, 23, 24]. However, considering the benefits that it could bring, it is worth trying to develop novel technologies and methods for breath analysis.

For the assessment of the food impact on breath VOCs, some pioneer steps in the breath research area have been established. Some studies examined different diet types and their impact on exhaled breath VOCs – i.e., the impact of long-term vegan diet [25], gluten-free diet [26], ketogenic diet [27], high-protein diet [28], low fiber and high fiber diets [29, 30], whole grain diet

[31]. Even more detailed metabolomic studies employed breath analysis – e.g., to determine tricarboxylic acid cycle (TCA) metabolites [32], omega-oxidation products of aliphatic fatty acids [33], the impact of the conjugated linoleic acid (CLA) on fat and starch digestion [34] or the impact of nutrition on metabolic pathways [35]. Additionally, the relationship between some of the exhaled breath VOCs and diet-related metabolism disorders has been established [16, 36, 37, 38]. Among them, widely present are overweight and obesity, which are often wrongly mixed up in common speech. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), both disorders are defined as abnormal with excessive fat accumulation, while the difference is in the quantity of that excess [39]. Body mass index (BMI) is an adopted measure for a rough estimation of body weight and height ratio, and it is used for the distinguishment of overweight and obesity. Persons who have $BMI \geq 25$ are considered overweight, and those who have $BMI \geq 30$ are with obesity [39]. Furthermore, diabetes mellitus type 2 is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by high glucose levels, upon lack of insulin production or insulin effectiveness due to the body's resistance to it [40]. This high level of glucose leads to damage to the blood vessels, kidneys, and heart and can cause severe cardiovascular diseases [40]. Listed metabolic disorders have been investigated a lot, and there are many propositions for potential breath volatile biomarkers for overweight and obesity [41], diabetes [15], and cardiovascular diseases [42]. Additionally, there are indices that breath analysis can be affected by lifestyle habits. Few studies reported the impact of age, gender [43][39], and lifestyle habits on specific breath VOCs [37, 44] Also, one recent study examined different factors that can impact breath VOC profile (not specific VOCs), and indicated that smoking habit, age, gender, and BMI showed statistically significant impact [45].

Conventionally, breath analysis is performed using gas chromatography with mass spectrometry (GC-MS). Although it is the most reliable technique for breath analysis, it has a few drawbacks – bulky instrumentation, high price, and cannot be used for on-site analysis [46]. In common use in breath analysis are SIFT-MS and PTR-MS techniques which do enable real-time monitoring and direct analysis [46]. Furthermore, there are existing portable devices used in exhaled breath analysis, as well; these are mainly mass spectrometers, but also FT-IR spectrometers, and various e-Noses [46]. However, the development of novel small, affordable, and portable solutions is always highly desirable in order to enable wider breath analysis applications. Recently, a portable membrane-inlet mass spectrometric (MIMS) device has been validated for a food impact assessment on breath VOCs in the healthy population [47]. This instrument enables online and offline analysis and direct sampling without sample preparation. Limits of detection are at ppb_v level for currently examined breath VOCs [47]. Also, it has very low power consumption and it is suitable for in-field applications. Finally, it has a short analysis time (~1 min) across the mass range m/z 35-200. Taking in mind all these properties, it showed a potential to be used as a breath VOC screening tool and deserves to be more explored in the breath research area [47].

The aim of the current study was the employment of the portable MIMS system for the examination of the impact of the common standardized meal, and some lifestyle parameters and habits on breath VOCs in different populations. The study involved people who have poor-quality diets (lack of vegetables and fruit, dealing with vitamin deficiencies, etc.), people with metabolic disorders – overweight, obesity, diabetes type 2, cardiovascular diseases, and healthy professional

athletes. Athletes represent a healthy population, and they were mainly involved in inspecting different lifestyle factors as physical activity rate or alcohol/tobacco consumption. As the MIMS system was previously validated in the general adult healthy population [47], results from this study will be compared to those and enrich the findings.

Materials and Methods

Analytes selection

To accomplish the aim of the study several VOCs related to food metabolism were analyzed. Considering the technical possibilities of a portable MIMS system, four exhaled breath VOCs were selected for monitoring – acetone, ethanol, isoprene, and n-pentane. They were selected for several reasons. Namely, it is known that they have endogenous origin in human exhaled breath. Also, all four are believed to be related to food macronutrient metabolism. Acetone is a ketone, produced by the body during fat metabolism by breaking the free fatty acids [13]. In the state of reduced glucose level (e.g., starvation) acetone production is increased [48], as the organism seeks other sources of energy when sugar is not available [49]. Also, in the state of the metabolic disorder (i.e., T2DM), despite sufficient sugar consumption, the decomposition of glucose is decreased due to the cell resistance to insulin, or lack of insulin production. Consequently, the organism starts to decompose fat, although there is glucose unused, and increased breath acetone occurs. Thus, acetone level is prominent potential biomarker for T2DM [50]. Also, there are indices that breath acetone differs in people with overweight and obesity, and it has been used for fat loss monitoring, as its level increases with lowering the weight [49]. Isoprene is known as a by-product of cholesterol biosynthesis [13]. It is mainly produced in the muscle tissue [51]. It was speculated that isoprene can be biomarker for diabetes, along with the acetone, but it was not confirmed yet, as isoprene biochemical pathway is not fully clear [51]. However, there is potential to monitor breath isoprene in some CVD treatments that require lowering the cholesterol level [42]. Also, it has been noticed that isoprene breath level is increased upon physical activity [13]. Ethanol is a product of mouth and gut bacteria, and it is related to the metabolism of unabsorbed carbohydrates [14, 52, 53]. n-Pentane has been associated with the state of stress, inflammation, and lipid peroxidation, which could be increased upon deficiency of vitamin E from the diet [13, 54]. It is proved that oxidative stress is related to T2DM and CVD [55]. Also, n-pentane is increased upon tissue injury, and it could be monitored during acute myocardial infarction or other CVD injury [42]. Thus, selected breath VOCs are considered potential biomarkers for diet-related metabolic disorders.

As mentioned previously, some of these VOCs are related to physical activity, or other lifestyle parameters, which we aimed to inspect. The impact of physical activity on breath acetone [7, 56, 57] and isoprene [57, 58, 59] levels were confirmed, as well as cigarette consumption impact on breath acetone [60] and n-pentane [61] levels. Age impact previously was noticed for breath isoprene [42], n-pentane [62], and ethanol [63] levels. Gender impact was observed for breath acetone [43, 47], isoprene [42] and ethanol [63], while n-pentane was not affected by this factor [64]. In several studies BMI impact on breath acetone, ethanol, and isoprene was examined, but no direct correlation with any of these specific breath VOCs was observed [43, 65, 66, 67]. However, there is study that indicated the difference in breath profile of healthy and

overweight/obese population [68]. Namely, among other compounds, they reported that breath isoprene level was greater in children with overweight and obesity compared to healthy controls [68].

All these previous findings indicate that the impact of diet and lifestyle habits on selected breath VOCs is legitimate and needs to be examined more.

Participants recruitment

Participants who donated exhaled breath samples in this study were recruited from four European countries – the United Kingdom, Greece, Germany, and Belgium. All the participants provided their written consent after they had received information about the research in written and oral form. A list of ethical approvals for conducting the pilot studies is given in the *Compliance of ethical standards* section, at the end of the article. The investigation was done by the current European *General Data Protection Regulation*. Along with the exhaled breath samples, all the participants filled out a questionnaire where they answered questions regarding their gender, age, type of living and working environment, frequency of physical activity, diet type, alcohol, and cigarette consumption habits. The recruitment strategy that was used for this study had a number of aspects including emails sent to local staff and students, text messages sent to patients by GP practices, local newsletters, flyers and posters in the local area such as gyms, supermarkets, council boards and local shops, and regular posts on social media sites.

Data collected via questionnaire are presented in Figure 1 for all 151 participants, and in Table 2 for all examined participant groups separately. Exhaled breath samples and corresponding questionnaires were pseudo-anonymized, analyzed, and processed as such. General information on the recruitment process is presented in Table 1, along with the general and population-specific inclusion criteria for participation in this study. People with type 2 diabetes mellitus and cardiovascular disease were earlier patients in medical institutions in corresponding countries listed in Table 1, thus their diagnoses were known to the experts who conducted the recruitment. Type 2 diabetes mellitus participants involved in the study were not under insulin therapy. Thus, they did not change their treatment during this study. Body mass index (BMI) values were calculated upon measurements in the institutions where recruitment was done.

Table 1. General information for participants' recruitment during the VOC study. *Inclusion criteria that do not apply to user groups People with T2DM and People with CVD.

Participant category	No.	Country	Period	General inclusion criteria	Specific inclusion criteria
People with overweight	33	United Kingdom Greece	December 2021-March 2022 March-May 2022	Being a minimum of 18 years old. Able to sign informed consent. Able to come to the sampling office.	Having BMI between 25 and 30.
People with obesity	22	Greece	April-May 2022	Able to perform continuous exhalation for the 30s.	Having BMI greater than 30.
People with T2DM	11	Germany	August-November 2022	Currently not pregnant or breastfeeding.	Diagnosed diabetes type 2.
People with CVD	21	Belgium	May-October 2022	Able to consume standard breakfast provided.	Diagnosed cardiovascular disease.

People with poor-quality diet	40	United Kingdom	December 2021-March 2022	Not have any respiratory infections or diseases. *In good general health, without chronic diseases	Having less than 2 portions of fruit and vegetables per day or being diagnosed with iron deficiency.
Athletes	24	Greece	March-April 2022	*Not taking medications from the following groups: proton pump inhibitors, statins, antidepressants, medication for asthma, diabetes, high blood pressure.	Being a professional athlete, i.e., being involved in a professional sport club and having more than 5 professional trainings per week.

Figure 1. Summary of the data collected from 151 participants about their lifestyle via questionnaire. (COLOR ONLINE ONLY)

Table 2. Data collected from the participants about their lifestyle via questionnaire by examined participants groups and evaluated categorical parameters.

Categorical parameter		Number of participants					
		OW	OB	T2DM	CVD	PQD	AT
Gender	Female	24	14	5	8	28	23

	Male	9	8	6	13	12	1
Age	18-40	21	8	1	2	31	23
	41-60	11	11	7	6	9	1
	<60	1	3	3	13		
Living environment	Urban	27	18	9	9	33	21
	Rural	6	4	2	12	7	3
Working environment	Urban	26	19	9	7	34	11
	Rural	7	3	2		5	13
	Retired				14	1	
Alcohol consumption	No	11	6	8	11	16	5
	< 2 drinks/week	13	11	2	2	14	13
	2-8 drinks/week	8	5	1	7	10	6
	>8 drinks/week	1			1		
Smoking habits	No	29	15	9	21	39	19
	< 5 cigarettes/day		1				4
	5-20 cigarettes/day	4	6	1		1	1
	> 20 cigarettes/day			1			
Diet habits	Omnivore	30	22	10	19	32	23
	Vegetarian	3			1	5	1
	Vegan			1	1	3	
Physical activity habits	Low	14	17	7	6	19	
	Moderate	17	4	3	9	11	
	High	2	1	1	6	10	
	Professional athlete						24
BMI	Underweight (<18.5) *				2	2	
	Normal weight (18.5-24.9) *			3	6	18	24
	Overweight (25-29.9) *	33		2	6	15	
	Obese (>30) *		22	6	7	5	
BMI values range		25-30	30-46	22-44	18-38	18-38	19-24

*Criteria set according to the WHO classification [69].

Sampling procedure

Every participant agreed to come to the partner institutions in corresponding countries listed in Table 1, and to provide one exhaled breath sample before the meal – after about 12h of food and beverages restraint (only pure still water was allowed), and one sample 120 min after the meal. The time between meal consumption and the second sample collection was set to 120 min as previously it was shown to be the optimal time point for observing the changes in selected breath VOCs [47]. Consumption of cigarettes and chewing gums were also not allowed. Participants were asked to brush their teeth in the morning regularly, as we decided that it will have less impact on our analytes of interest than overnight bacterial activity in the oral cavity. There were no experimental or observational checks on the fulfilment of the requirements. Before the sampling the participants were asked to self-report if they had followed the protocol requirements. By signing the consent form, they declared that the requirements were followed.

Samples of the whole exhaled breath were collected in 1L Tedlar® bags. Participants were asked to first calm their breathing with 2 deep inhalations on their nose and exhalations on their mouth, followed by the third very deep inhalation and one long exhalation into the sampling bag. The bags were filled up to about 80% of the total volume. Samples were sealed in the sampling bags and have been sent to Serbia by courier and analyzed right upon the arrival, within 24-48h. Stability of breath VOCs in Tedlar® bags was proved to be up to 3 days for aldehydes and hydrocarbons (e.g., isoprene, n-pentane), and even up to 7 days for ketones (e.g., acetone) [56, 70]. Prior to the analysis, samples were tempered at 36-37°C for half an hour. Along with the exhaled breath samples, the room air sample was collected as a control blank sample.

Standardized meal

All the participants consumed provided standardized meals which was a common breakfast in European cultures. As the recruitment of the participants was conducted in different countries, it was not possible to provide the same meal. It contained bread with butter/margarine, jam, yogurt, and/or orange juice. All the macronutrients were included in sufficient amounts, and yet it was not too complex. The content of macronutrients and energy values for meals in different countries is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Standardized meal macronutrient content and energetic properties.

Participant category	Country	Carbohydrates content (%)	Protein content (%)	Fat content (%)	Energy (kcal)
People with overweight	Greece, UK	63.4	10.8	2.8	324
People with obesity	Greece				
People with poor-quality diet	UK				
Athletes	Greece				
People with T2DM	Germany	55.1	12.0	12.8	397
People with CVD	Belgium	78.6	17.2	12.0	480

Reagents and Material

Pure chemical liquids used in this research were: acetone (CAS 67-64-1, Sigma Aldrich, ≥99.5%), ethanol (CAS 64-17-5, Honeywell, >99.8%), isoprene (CAS 78-79-5, Sigma Aldrich, ≥99.5%) and n-pentane (CAS 109-66-0, Sigma Aldrich, ≥99%), methanol (CAS 67-56-1, Sigma Aldrich, >99.8%) in the liquid phase. Sampling 1L Tedlar® bags were purchased from Zefon International. A thermostat chamber was purchased from Memmert GmbH + Co.KG. IKA®-Werke GmbH & Co. KG automatic micropipette was used. Sheet membrane SIL-TEC A class VI USP medical grade polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) was purchased from Technical product Inc. of GA. Parafilm M was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Groceries for the preparation of standardized meals were purchased in local supermarkets.

Instrumentation

The MIMS instrument employed in this pilot study is based on the membrane-inlet mass spectrometry principle. It has 5 main parts: sample inlet, ion source, mass analyzer, electronic control unit (ECU), and a laptop for processing the obtained signals. The sample inlet is a stainless-steel probe with a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) sheet membrane. This membrane represents the only barrier between the atmosphere and the core of the instrument. It selectively passes the volatile compounds to the closed electron impact ion source where the ionization process occurs. Ionized molecules are directed by lenses into the single quadrupole mass analyzer from where they are forwarded onto a secondary

electron multiplier (SEM) detector. Ion currents signals which are detected for certain mass fragments are multiplied by the SEM and processed with the ECU. It provides unit resolution across the m/z 300 mass range, low ppb detection limits, fast response, and short analysis run time (about 1 min). Also, it enables selected ion monitoring (SIM) and full scan mode. These properties make this instrument a suitable candidate for breath VOC analyses. With its small dimensions – 616x220x433 mm (LxHxW), weight of 23 kg, and low power consumption (<200 W/h) it can be portable. Additionally, it does not require sample preparation and it can be used for online analysis, as well. The functionality of this system and its capability for employment in breath VOC analysis was described in more detail elsewhere [47]. Also, a novel bioanalytical method for exhaled breath acetone, ethanol, isoprene, and n-pentane was established using this instrument [47]. The experimental setup during the exhaled breath samples analysis is presented in Figure 2. Tedlar® bags containing exhaled breath samples were connected to the membrane inlet of the instrument via a small perfluoro-alkoxy (PFA) hose wrapped in a thermostable Teflon® tape.

Figure 2. The experimental setup for exhaled breath analysis using portable MIMS system; a) Tedlar® bag filled with exhaled breath, b) membrane probe heated at 70°C, c) portable MIMS system, d) laptop for monitoring analysis and data processing. Adjusted from [47]. Figure was originally published under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>. (COLOR ONLINE ONLY)

Analysis

Breath samples collected from recruited participants were analyzed in batches during the 12 months – from December 2021 until November 2022. A laboratory air sample was analyzed each time – during calibration and sample analyses, in the SIM and full scan mode (m/z 10-200). All calibrants' and samples' ion current signals obtained were normalized to the ion current signal obtained for the m/z 14 from the scanned air sample analyzed on the same day. The m/z 14 was chosen as it originates from the air nitrogen and compared to m/z 28 (also from the air nitrogen) does not interfere with mass fragments of interest in this study. This routine was established to

eliminate variations that could originate from the changes in the instrument stability over time. Relative intensities obtained after the normalization were used for the quantification.

Preparation of calibration gas standards for acetone, ethanol, isoprene, and n-pentane was conducted according to the static dilution method previously described [47, 71]. For each VOC analyte, liquid stock and working methanolic solutions were freshly prepared. Using the micropipette adequate aliquots of VOCs liquid working solutions were added to 1L glass flasks. Right upon the pipetting the flasks were sealed with several parafilm layers and left in a thermostat chamber at 36-37°C for VOCs to evaporate in the gas phase. Gas standards for selected VOCs were analyzed separately in SIM and full scan modes. Calibration curves for each analyte were fitted in the in-house developed Python application using the signals obtained from SIM scan mode, according to the previously described method [47]. Namely, the application was programmed to extract the maximal ion currents for monitored analytes and to normalize these to the maximal ion current obtained for m/z 14. Then, it would use these calculated relative intensities to generate linear calibration curves using the linear regression with the least square model.

All samples were scanned in the full scan mode (m/z 35-200) in triplicates and in selected ion monitoring (SIM) mode for selected characteristic mass fragments – m/z 43 and m/z 58 for acetone, m/z 45 for ethanol, m/z 41 and m/z 42 for n-pentane, and m/z 67 for isoprene. Raw ion current data on VOC levels were processed via an in-house developed Python application for generating the ppb_v concentration levels from previously fitted calibration curves. This application was set to compare relative intensity signals obtained for selected m/z values in exhaled breath samples against the fitted calibration curves for the same mass fragments [47]. The limits of detection of the used method were 10 ppb_v for acetone and ethanol, 25 ppb_v for isoprene, and 5 ppb_v for n-pentane [47].

Food and lifestyle assessment

Food and lifestyle impacts on selected exhaled breath VOCs were evaluated using an experimentally obtained ppb_v levels for acetone, ethanol, isoprene and n-pentane, and data collected via questionnaire.

Food impact was assessed using the experimentally obtained exhaled breath concentrations of acetone, ethanol, isoprene, and n-pentane in exhaled breath samples collected before and 120 min after the meal. For each participant in this study, a ratio between VOC concentration after the meal and VOC concentration before the meal was determined. These ratios were calculated for each examined VOC and are called comparison factors (CF). If the value of CF was 1±10 % it was not considered a notable change in VOC level. In cases when there was more than a 10 % increase or decrease in CF, (i.e., VOC level) upon meal consumption, it was considered a notable change. The limit for the notable change in VOC signal was set according to the determined repeatability within the 3 measurements of the same breath sample. Furthermore, calculated comparison factors are used along with the questionnaire answers in One-way ANOVA on ranks (Kruskal-Wallis) test [72] to reveal possible statistically significant differences among examined categories.

Assessment of the lifestyle impact was examined using the experimentally obtained basal ppb_v values extracted from breath samples collected before the meal. These VOCs concentrations

are compared to the information collected via questionnaire and One-way ANOVA on ranks (Kruskal-Wallis) [72] statistical test was applied.

Results and Discussion

Exhaled breath VOC quantification

Exhaled breath acetone, ethanol, isoprene, and n-pentane levels were obtained from breath samples collected before the meal, and 120 min after the meal, for all recruited participants. For the calculation of the mean values per participants category experimentally obtained SIM signals were used. In cases where a large number of obtained results were below the limit of detection (e.g., for n-pentane), a LOD/2 value was used as a numerical value instead these missing values in the dataset, to contain the amount of data for statistical processing. Along with the breath samples, certain data about the participants lifestyle was collected. Table 4 represents obtained ppb_v levels across the examined questionnaire categorical parameters.

Table 4. Distribution of the experimentally obtained exhaled breath VOC levels by examined questionnaire categorical parameters.

Questionnaire vs. ppbv VOC levels			Acetone		Ethanol		Isoprene		n-Pentane	
Categorical parameter	Examined categories	Participants No.	BM	AM	BM	AM	BM	AM	BM	AM
Gender	Female	102	712	557	331	336	164	170	21	18
	Male	49	441	459	382	392	197	234	17	17
Age	18-40	86	538	539	316	329	154	159	21	18
	41-60	45	554	510	382	352	201	226	21	18
	>60	20	1151	501	405	471	205	253	15	14
Living environment	Urban	117	668	551	341	352	176	179	20	18
	Rural	34	471	437	370	364	172	232	21	18
Working environment	Urban	106	661	511	352	355	179	190	21	18
	Rural	30	587	632	250	274	160	158	20	21
	Retired	15	436	409	511	513	170	264	12	13
Alcohol drinking habit	No	57	776	495	419	420	188	200	20	16
	<2 drinks/week	55	554	552	324	297	161	170	21	18
	2-8 drinks/week	37	516	552	276	340	172	208	19	20
	>8 drinks/week	2	225	152	288	313	208	213	3	8
Cigarettes consumption habit	No	132	509	508	353	361	172	193	20	18
	<5 cig./day	5	679	642	207	211	163	160	14	15
	5-20 cig./day	13	679	669	310	324	179	178	17	18
	>20 cig./day	1	14865	333	738	639	504	287	108	13
Physical activity	Low	63	704	506	346	385	184	194	19	19
	Moderate	44	595	537	430	392	184	215	23	19
	High	20	335	419	344	382	161	186	19	16
	Pro	24	707	642	202	184	146	143	16	14

From the Table 4 it can be seen that there is one result that stands out (value 14865 ppb_v). This was obtained for acetone in the sample before meal for one participant who consume more than 20 cigarettes per day. This participant belonged to the T2DM group. As this value represents a great outlier, it was excluded from the calculations and statistical tests.

Table 5 presents acetone, ethanol, isoprene, and n-pentane mean ppb_v values, median ppb_v values, interquartile ranges, and standard deviations as a measure of variability. Relative standard deviation (RSD) among three consecutive full scan measurements for selected *m/z* values was calculated for all the examined samples. Average RSD values were: 8% for acetone, 5% for ethanol, 8% for isoprene, and 4% for n-pentane, which align with previously determined RSDs during the method validation [47]. Figure 3 is a graphical display of the mean ppb_v of listed breath VOCs for all the examined population groups.

Table 5. Mean and median ppb_v concentration levels, interquartile ranges and standard deviations obtained for acetone, isoprene, ethanol, and n-pentane for 151 participants from 6 user groups: 33 people with overweight (OW), 22 people with obesity (OB), 11 people with diabetes mellitus type 2 (T2DM), 21 people with cardiovascular disease (CVD), 40 people with poor-quality diet (PQD) and 24 athletes (AT), in samples collected before the meal (BM) and after the meal (AM).

VOC	Participant category	Number of participants	BM mean conc. (ppb _v)	BM median conc. (ppb _v)	BM interquartile range (ppb _v)	BM STD (ppb)	AM mean conc. (ppb _v)	AM median conc. (ppb _v)	AM interquartile range (ppb _v)	AM STD (ppb _v)
ACETONE	People with overweight	33	674	660	509-863	374	586	685	327-853	323
	People with obesity	22	737	761	683-828	170	751	763	687-881	160
	People with T2DM*	10	441	438	226-485	351	466	358	281-475	454
	People with CVD	21	499	337	101-800	522	544	245	155-638	582
	People with poor-quality diet	40	227	179	48-317	218	291	211	99-436	263
	Athletes	24	707	717	543-886	273	642	682	413-823	241
ETHANOL	People with overweight	33	342	325	207-445	166	308	290	148-380	215
	People with obesity	22	301	326	280-360	96	318	325	303-369	79
	People with T2DM	11	464	458	353-582	163	473	478	395-578	125
	People with CVD	21	474	452	314-689	259	493	480	377-565	174
	People with poor-quality diet	40	366	236	103-661	310	410	283	183-568	308
	Athletes	24	202	217	111-285	113	184	210	69-296	117
ISOPRENE	People with overweight	33	148	146	100-189	93	132	134	92-176	57
	People with obesity	22	235	227	170-345	94	233	224	168-333	94
	People with T2DM	11	215	186	62-339	178	182	171	74-278	136
	People with CVD	21	250	121	13-319	330	388	304	151-403	367
	People with poor-quality diet	40	130	136	94-161	59	144	150	107-186	69
	Athletes	24	146	146	104-178	51	143	142	107-182	56
n-PENTANE	People with overweight	33	24	24	12-33	17	20	21	10-28	14

People with obesity	22	20	21	17-24	8	21	21	17-27	8
People with T2DM	11	20	14	7-16	30	13	13	9-16	6
People with CVD	21	11	11	3-19	8	12	11	3-18	8
People with poor-quality diet	40	24	19	3-28	24	21	24	6-30	14
Athletes	24	16	17	9-23	10	14	16	3-22	10

*For T2DM category for acetone results were calculated for 10 participants, due to exclusion of one great outlier.

Figure 3. Bar graph presentation of mean ppbv concentration levels obtained for acetone, isoprene, ethanol, and n-pentane for 151 participants from 6 user groups: 33 people with overweight (OW), 22 people with obesity (OB), 11 (10 for acetone) people with diabetes mellitus type 2 (T2DM), 21 people with cardiovascular disease (CVD), 40 people with poor-quality diet (PQD) and 24 athletes (AT). (COLOR ONLINE ONLY)

Figure 4. Boxplot presentation of median ppb_v concentration levels and interquartile ranges obtained for acetone, isoprene, ethanol, and n-pentane for 151 participants from 6 user groups: 33 people with overweight (OW), 22 people with obesity (OB), 11 (10 for acetone) people with diabetes mellitus type 2 (T2DM), 21 people with cardiovascular disease (CVD), 40 people with poor-quality diet (PQD) and 24 athletes (AT). The outstanding value 14865 ppb_v obtained for acetone is excluded from the graph for clearer interpretation. (COLOR ONLINE ONLY)

Acetone quantification

The acetone mean level obtained in breath samples collected before the meal in overweight people was 674 ppb_v , while in samples collected after the meal, it was 586 ppb_v . In people with obesity, acetone level was slightly higher – 737 ppb_v in samples collected before the meal, and 751 ppb_v in samples collected after the meal. Additionally, in people with diabetes mellitus type 2 acetone level was 441 ppb_v in basal breath samples, and 466 ppb_v in samples collected after the meal. There are indices that breath acetone is increased in people with T2DM. Previously an increased level of exhaled breath acetone in children with obesity compared to lean controls was reported [68]. Also, it is well known that breath acetone is increased in T2DM patients with mean levels ~ 0.9 -1.8 ppm_v

[36] and which can go even up to ~ 10 ppm_v [73]. This study does not follow these indices. However, it must be noted that in this study only 10 participants were recruited for T2DM group. Certainly, the larger cohort of participants with T2DM would provide more relevant results. In the study of Turner *et al.* [43], it was reported that there is no significant impact of BMI on breath acetone level. In the named study healthy participants were recruited and it is not fully comparable with the current results. Given that in the current study breath acetone levels for people with overweight and obesity were not greatly different, it may be assumed that there is no direct BMI impact on breath acetone. It is rather dependent on glucose and insulin levels, which can be related to BMI, but not in all cases. No BMI correlation with breath acetone level was reported in the study of Schwarz *et al.*, as well [74]. One study reported that breath acetone concentration is increased in people with lower body fat percentage and lower BMI [75]. Due to the variations in reporting, we can assume that acetone increment is rather a consequence of increased body fat, than directly influenced by the BMI.

For people with cardiovascular disease mean breath acetone level was determined to be 449 ppb_v before the meal, and 544 ppb_v after the meal. So far, there are some reports on increased breath acetone just in patients with heart failure [76, 77]. However, participants with CVD in this study were mixed – there were people with hypertension, and high blood cholesterol and just one stated to have heart failure. All the participants were under adequate therapy at the time of sampling. Thus, our results are not comparable with previous findings, but generally, we did not notice an elevation in breath acetone in our CVD participants.

Furthermore, in people with a poor-quality diet, mean breath acetone levels were 227 and 291 ppb_v in samples before and after the meal, respectively. To the authors' best knowledge, this is the first report of acetone levels in this specific population, so there is no data to compare. There is only implication that breath ethane level is reduced as a consequence of a diet rich in fruit and vegetables [13], but there are no findings on examined VOCs. Although, if we assume that a poor-quality diet means a diet without fruit and vegetables, we can say that it should imply low simple sugars intake, and possibly increased acetone level. However, we noticed the opposite – in this category breath acetone level was the lowest among examined populations. The reasons may vary, as there is no detailed information on their regular diet – e.g., maybe it is rich in complex carbohydrates (i.e., starch) with a high glycemic index, or there could be another reason for a lower acetone level. Table 2 shows that half of the participants with the poor-quality diet were overweight or obese. That may support the assumption that their diet could be rich in complex carbohydrates e.g., from unhealthy foods, which could decrease acetone level.

Professional athletes showed mean breath acetone levels to be 707 ppb_v in samples collected before the meal and 642 ppb_v in samples collected after the meal. There is no previous reporting for breath acetone levels specifically for professional athletes, but obtained levels are similar to the previously obtained levels using the same technique and method for healthy people [47]. There is an indication that breath acetone level is increased during exercise [7, 56], but it is not known if there is a long-term impact on the level. Results from this study show that there is no prolonged increase in breath acetone levels for athletes.

One recent study examined breath acetone concentration in seven healthy participants during fasting and after eating different meal types [78]. The balanced meal type from named study was the most similar to the meal provided in this study. They reported that breath acetone slightly decreased upon balanced meal consumption [78]. In this study a decrement in acetone level was observed in people with overweight, T2DM and professional athletes. This inconsistency may have happened as different population groups are examined. Also, the number of samples was very different in the two studies, thus they may not be fully comparable.

Ethanol quantification

Ethanol mean levels in breath samples collected before and after the meal in participants with overweight were 342 ppb_v and 308 ppb_v, respectively. For participants with obesity, these values were 301 ppb_v and 318 ppb_v. As can be seen, there is no great difference between participants of these two categories. In participants with type 2 diabetes mellitus measured values were 464 ppb_v before the meal, and 473 ppb_v after the meal. Ethanol levels in participants with diagnosed CVD were 474 ppb_v in breath samples collected before the meal, and 493 ppb_v in breath samples collected after the meal. Furthermore, basal breath ethanol level in people with poor-quality diet was measured to be 366 ppb_v, while after the meal it increased to 410 ppb_v. For professional athletes, these values were 202 ppb_v and 184 ppb_v, respectively. These levels can be compared to the previously reported values for the healthy population using the same technique. The values were 488 ppb_v in breath samples collected before the meal, and 474 ppb_v in samples collected after the meal [47]. Another study reported mean breath ethanol levels in healthy population to be 50-100 ppb before meal, and 100-400 after the protein-calorie meal [28]. It must be noticed that in the referred study a different meal type was examined. Ethanol is known to be related to gut bacterial activity and the metabolism of unabsorbed carbohydrates [13], thus meal with higher carbohydrate content could cause greater breath ethanol concentration. Also, there are previous indications that breath ethanol is increased in people with obesity [79] and in people with T2DM [80]. This may be the reason for lower ethanol level in athletes, who have BMI<25. If we assume that professional athletes in general have faster digestion and healthier metabolism as a consequence of regularly increased physical activity, it could explain lower levels of ethanol in athletes. For people with CVD and poor-quality diet, there are no reported breath ethanol values to the authors' knowledge. In general, ethanol basal concentrations in the current study were slightly higher than previously reported for healthy population [81]. Such results may originate from the fact that fragment *m/z* 45 was used for ethanol quantification mass, which is common for 2-propanol, which can be present in exhaled breath in lower concentration and could have contributed. Also, in this study different participant groups are examined. Thus, the results may not be fully comparable. Finally, a great amount of breath ethanol originates from oral bacteria [52, 82], which can impact the amount of endogenous ethanol, independently of the population group. The overall impression is that there was no great difference in breath ethanol concentration before and 120 min upon food ingestion. It is known that breath ethanol peaks shortly after food ingestion, within the first hour [28, 47]. Thus, it can be that the greatest peak is missed in this study. But, during the method validation 120 min time point was chosen to be optimal for monitoring the food impact on the group of selected analytes [47].

Isoprene quantification

Isoprene mean level in participants with overweight were 148 ppb_v and 132 ppb_v, in breath samples before and after the meal, respectively. In participants with obesity, these values were higher – 235 ppb_v before the meal, and 233 ppb_v after the meal. Increased level of isoprene was also noticed in participants who have diabetes mellitus type 2 and CVD. Isoprene levels determined in breath samples collected before the meal were 215 ppb_v for people with T2DM and 250 ppb_v for CVD patients. On the other hand, 182 ppb_v was measured in samples after the meal in T2DM participants and 388 ppb_v in CVD participants. Isoprene is a by-product of cholesterol synthesis [14], which may relate to metabolic disorders in lipid metabolism which is well established in named conditions [42]. Also, isoprene is known to be a potential biomarker for diabetes [36]. Additionally, the study of Biagini *et al.* showed that breath isoprene is increased in patients with heart failure [77]. Furthermore, obtained isoprene levels for participants with poor-quality diet was 130 ppb_v in breath samples before the meal and 144 ppb_v in samples after the meal. According to the literature, there are no previous findings on breath isoprene in this specific population. Finally, mean isoprene levels in breath samples from professional athletes were 146 ppb_v in samples collected before the meal, and 143 ppb_v in samples after the meal. These levels can be compared to the levels obtained for the healthy population by the same technique and method – 70 ppb_v before the meal and 66 ppb_v after the meal [47]. Also, in the study of Kushch *et al.* mean breath isoprene level was reported to be 99 ppb in healthy participants [67]. It can be concluded that isoprene level is increased in participants who have a more active lifestyle, i.e., more physical activity, compared to a generally healthy population. Recent studies monitored breath isoprene constantly during extensive physical activity and reported an increase in breath isoprene immediately upon the start of the physical activity. However, it is reduced during the exercise and reaches a level even below the level at the start of the training [58, 59, 66, 83]. In our study, we did not monitor isoprene levels during the training, nor did athletes have any physical activity during the study. On the other side, there is a study that reported mean breath isoprene level to be 212 ppb in healthy population [53]. This value is higher than those for the athletes in the current study and does not support the fact that breath isoprene is increased in people with increased physical activity. Thus, this needs to be inspected more in more focused studies to conclude if there is a prolonged impact of increased physical activity on breath isoprene level.

n-Pentane quantification

The mean n-pentane level in participants with overweight obtained in breath collected before the meal was 24 ppb_v, while in samples collected after the meal that value was 20 ppb_v. For the participants with obesity, these levels were 20 ppb_v and 21 ppb_v, respectively, while for participants with diabetes mellitus type 2, these levels were 20 ppb_v before the meal and 13 ppb_v after the meal. In participants who suffer from CVD, the basal level of n-pentane was 11 ppb_v, while the postprandial level was 12 ppb_v. Additionally, the n-pentane level for people with poor-quality diets was 24 ppb_v in samples before the meal, and 21 ppb_v in samples collected after the meal. Finally, in professional athletes, n-pentane levels were 16 ppb_v determined before the meal, and 14 ppb_v in samples after the meal.

This is the first time that breath n-pentane levels are reported by these specific categories, to the authors' best knowledge. In comparison with n-pentane levels previously obtained for healthy

populations using the same method – 9 ppb_v before the meal and 8 ppb_v after the meal [47] an increase in n-pentane levels was examined in populations in this study. As n-pentane is a marker for oxidative stress and lipid peroxidation [84], it was assumed that it could be increased in people with metabolic disorders. Additionally, one recent study examined the difference between the vegan and Mediterranean diet and showed that people who do not consume animal products (i.e., have plant-based diet) have a lower level of breath n-pentane [25]. As one of our examined populations is people whose diet is poor in plants, this may explain the increased level of n-pentane, compared to healthy participants. Also, we noticed higher levels of breath n-pentane in populations with increased BMI and T2DM patients, while with CVD patients and athletes, the levels were not significantly increased. It was initially surprising that breath n-pentane levels did not go up for CVD patients. However, n-pentane concentration represents the overall oxidative stress in an organism caused by long-term lifestyle habits, environment, diet quality, etc., thus it may be that some other factor contributed to such results.

It can be seen from the Table 5 that mean and median values differ for some of the examined categories and analytes. However, these are at the same level of magnitude. Thus, only mean exhaled breath VOC values were compared to the relevant references, as these were reported more often.

Food and lifestyle impact assessment

The food and lifestyle impact were assessed by combining the experimentally obtained ppb_v levels for breath VOC presented in Table 5, and the data about the participants' lifestyles collected via questionnaire presented in Figure 1.

Food impact assessment

Food impact was evaluated using calculated comparison factors, i.e., ratios between VOC concentrations after and before the meal. Comparison factors were calculated for all participants separately. Among all, only comparison factors that showed VOC signal change upon meal greater than 10 % were accepted as notable. This limit was set considering the maximal RSD value among examined analytes' signals which showed to be 8%, as reported in the text above. Quantitative presentation of the food impact is the amount of these “significantly”/noticeably altered VOC signals (i.e., comparison factors) among all examined participant, per all analytes (Table 6). It should be noted that in this case “significant” does not refer to statistical significance. This is rather an insight into the potential impact of the consumed meal on examined breath VOCs.

Table 6. Overview of comparison factors for breath acetone, ethanol, isoprene, and n-pentane across examined populations.

Participants category	The notable change upon meal consumption (%)			
	ACETONE	ETHANOL	ISOPRENE	n-PENTANE
People with overweight	76	88	58	79
People with obesity	50	59	23	59
People with Diabetes mellitus	60*	45	36	64

People with cardiovascular disease	81	67	76	62
People with poor-quality diet	78	88	45	70
Athletes	75	79	33	88
Total for all 151 participants	72	76	46	72

*For T2DM category for acetone results were calculated for 150 participants, due to exclusion of one great outlier.

From Table 6 it can be concluded that notable concentration change upon meal consumption was observed in ~75% of all participants for ethanol, 70% of all participants for acetone, and n-pentane, and ~45-50% for isoprene. These findings follow previously reported results for comparison factors upon meal consumption for the general adult healthy population for n-pentane and isoprene changes upon meal [47]. However, in this study the value for notable change for acetone and ethanol is lower, which may be due to the different meal that was provided to participants. In the referred study [47] a high carbohydrate meal was provided to participants, which can explain greater change in both, acetone, and ethanol levels – as these are related the carbohydrates metabolism [53, 78, 85].

ANOVA on ranks test results are presented in Table 7. These results provide insight into the statistically significant differences in selected VOCs changes upon meal consumption (i.e., comparison factors) among people with different characteristics and lifestyles.

Table 7. Food impact assessment expressed as one-way ANOVA on ranks statistical test results for examined categorical parameters versus calculated comparison factors. Bolded p-values imply the statistically significant difference between the breath VOC changes for specific categories since p-values are below the threshold ($\alpha=0.05$).

One-way ANOVA on ranks test		p-value			
Categorical parameter	Examined category	Acetone	Ethanol	Isoprene	n-Pentane
Participant category	OW vs. OB vs. T2DM vs. CVD vs. PQD vs. AT	0.446	0.583	3.02E-05	0.880
Gender	Male vs. Female	0.835	0.763	0.743	0.609
Age	18-40 vs 41-60 vs. >61	0.212	0.099	0.023	0.121
Living environment	Rural vs. Urban	0.681	0.961	0.001	0.094
Working environment	Rural vs. Urban	0.656	0.363	0.015	0.576
Physical activity	Low vs. Moderate vs. High vs. Pro	0.034	0.244	0.376	0.652
Alcohol drinking habits	No vs. <2 drinks/week vs. 2-8 drinks/week vs. > 8 drinks/week	0.408	0.568	0.893	0.330
Cigarettes consumption habit	No vs. <5 cig./day vs. 5-20 cig./day vs. >20 cig./day	0.931	0.736	0.273	0.338

Statistically significant concentration change upon meal was observed for acetone in participants with different physical activity habits. Also, isoprene level was altered differently in people of different population groups, people of different ages, and different living and working environments.

Previously, change in meal consumption was noticed only for acetone levels in participants who consume alcohol and those who do not [47]. That study included only 50 participants from the general healthy population. The current study complements it by examining the same categorical parameters for other groups of participants. The currently determined relationship

between change in acetone level upon meal consumption and physical activity rate does not have similar previous findings that could support it. However, it was said in the text above that breath acetone level could be altered by physical activity [7]. Also, one recent study examined mixed effect of balanced meal and physical activity in a healthy population [78]. They reported that breath acetone significantly increases after moderate exercise and consumption of balanced meal [78]. This supports our finding that there is some relationship between the physical activity rate and food impact on breath acetone. However, in our study participants did not have any training, thus these studies are only partially comparable. Regarding isoprene level change upon food consumption versus listed questionnaire categorical parameters, there are no previous findings, as well. As it was said in the text, isoprene can be related to lipid metabolism, to oxidative stress and it is a possible biomarker for diabetes mellitus [14, 36, 42, 77]. Examined populations differ in food macronutrient metabolism. Also, it is common knowledge that oxidative stress is related to aging and different environmental conditions. Thus, it could be assumed that these factors could contribute to the relationships revealed in this study. Previously reported studies examined the impact of different meal types [25, 28, 29]. To the authors' best knowledge, this is the first report on food impact in different populations.

The impact of several specific diet regimes on breath acetone level was examined previously. It was proved that breath acetone increases during fasting, low-carb and high-fat diets, i.e., in the state of ketosis [27, 86], while its concentration decreases upon high-carb (i.e., glucose), high-fiber and high-protein meals [28, 29, 85]. One recent study compared acetone level after ingestion of different meal types (high carbohydrate, high fat, high protein and balanced) against fasting in seven healthy participants [78]. They observed that fasting state and different meals caused different acetone concentration trends. Fasting and high-fat meals increased breath acetone level, while high-carb and balanced meals decreased it. The high-protein meal decreased breath acetone level, but its impact was the lowest among examined diet regimes. A balanced meal was the most similar to the one provided in this study, but still different [78]. The current study follows that one, as we observed lower acetone level upon meal consumption in healthy professional athletes, which represent a comparable population with one from that study.

For our other analytes the food impact was less examined, compared to the breath acetone. However, there are some findings. Ethanol increment is noticed shortly after some carbohydrate meal ingestion, most possibly due to the glucose digestion by the mouth flora [53]. Also, it was reported that high-protein meal and meal containing fibers tend to increase breath ethanol level [28, 29]. On the other side, Spacek *et al.* reported that breath ethanol is hardly related to food consumption [82]. They concluded that ethanol presence in the exhaled breath is rather consequence of the oral bacteria activity, than those from the distal small colon which are the main producers of ethanol from digested food [82]. However, on that occasion only high-protein meal was examined, thus it may not be an overall conclusion about the food impact on breath ethanol. More focused studies should be conducted on exhaled breath ethanol upon different foods consumption.

Measurement of the breath isoprene in fasting state and postprandially after ingestion of 75g of glucose showed no significant variation in its level related to blood glucose level [53]. High-

protein meal also did not affect the breath isoprene level [28]. Our results confirm that there is low or no significant impact on breath isoprene upon consumption of the meal provided in current study.

Food impact on breath n-pentane was poorly examined, so far. One recent study compared n-pentane levels in people who follow Mediterranean diet versus people who follow vegan diet [25]. It was reported that n-pentane level is lower in people pursuing vegan diet. Assumption is that it is caused by less oxidative stress in people who base their diet on plants [25]. In the current study we did not observe any statistically significant differences for n-pentane level change upon meal consumption among different examined populations. However, we do not have information on fruit and vegetables consumption for all examined populations to be able to support or dispute that study. We only have information that people with poor-quality diet have lack of fruit and vegetables in their regular diet. Given that quantified n-pentane concentrations (Table 5) are among the greatest in this population, we can hypothesize that amount of plants in diet impacts n-pentane breath level. Still, this needs to be examined more.

Generally, noticeable alteration in selected VOC levels upon meal consumption was observed for all analytes, except for isoprene. However, as the meal provided to all participants could not be the same (but rather similar) during this pilot study, we cannot say that these results can serve for direct comparison of the examined populations. At this point, these findings are evidence that our MIMS instrument can monitor food impact, and that some statistical differences are observed by examining specific populations separately versus reaction to the meal ingested. Further investigation should be focused on specific meal types in a single population and its control group.

Lifestyle impact assessment

ANOVA on ranks statistical test was applied to the exhaled breath acetone, ethanol, isoprene, and n-pentane basal versus data collected via questionnaire in order to assess the lifestyle impact. The results are presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Lifestyle impact assessment expressed as one-way ANOVA on ranks statistical test results for examined categorical parameters versus obtained basal exhaled breath VOCs concentrations. Bolded p-values imply the statistically significant difference between the breath VOCs changes for specific categories since p-values are below the threshold ($\alpha=0.05$).

One-way ANOVA on ranks test		p-value			
Categorical parameter	Examined category	Acetone	Ethanol	Isoprene	n-Pentane
Participant category	OW vs. OB vs. T2DM vs. CVD vs. PQD vs. AT	7.38E-10	4.00E-04	0.007	0.022
Gender	Male vs. Female	0.054	0.054	0.899	0.145
Age	18-40 vs 41-60 vs. >61	0.277	0.020	0.524	0.020
Living environment	Rural vs. Urban	0.231	0.250	0.288	0.297
Working environment	Rural vs. Urban	0.196	0.002	0.716	0.171
Physical activity	Low vs. Moderate vs. High vs. Pro	0.001	0.001	0.876	0.236
Alcohol drinking habits	No vs. <2 drinks/week vs. 2-8 drinks/week vs. >8 drinks/week	0.550	0.038	0.647	0.232
Cigarettes consumption habit	No vs. <5 cig./day vs. 5-20 cig./day vs. >20 cig./day	0.098	0.225	0.166	0.332

Considering the lifestyle impact and participants' answers via questionnaire, statistically significant differences were observed for all breath VOCs basal levels among all the examined population groups. Additionally, breath acetone level differs among people with different physical activity habits. Moreover, tendency for gender impact is noticed (value 0.054 in Table 8). There are previous indices that acetone level differs in males and females [43, 47], and that it is related to exercise [7]. Furthermore, the relationship between tobacco smoking and increased acetone level was reported before [47, 60]. Also, there is indication that age impacts breath acetone level [86]. However, in this study these dependencies were not observed. Furthermore, it can be observed that age, working environment, frequency of physical activity, and alcohol drinking habit may be related to breath ethanol level. Additionally, there is a tendency towards gender impact as well ($p=0.054$ in Table 8). There are no previous findings on the impact of any of these factors on breath ethanol levels. However, in one study ethanol elimination range in the function of age, gender, and drinking habit was evaluated [63]. It was concluded that mean breath ethanol elimination rates were higher in females, older participants, and those who drink more alcohol [63]. Also, in the study of Turner *et al.* [65], it was reported that there was no relation between the ethanol level of participants who drank alcoholic beverages the night before the breath sampling. In our study participants were asked to abstain from alcohol before sampling, thus this is not fully comparable. Also, the discovered statistical relation in our study possibly is not direct, but it may be that consumption of alcohol has an impact on gut flora and indirectly reflects on breath ethanol level. Finally, a statistically significant difference was observed for breath n-pentane levels among people of different ages. Given that n-pentane is a biomarker of lipid peroxidation and oxidative stress, it is logical that there is a difference between younger and older people. This follows the previous report on increased breath n-pentane level in older subjects [62, 64]. Except for the population group, we did not observe statistically significant differences in breath isoprene level for other categorical parameters. There are previous reports on isoprene variation in children and adults [87]. This study reveals the increase in breath isoprene level with age, until it reaches a stable level in adult population. In this current study only adult population is examined, thus this age dependence could not be observed. In the same study gender impact on isoprene level was examined, and no significant difference was noticed [87]. This finding is supported by study of Kushch *et al.* [67] and current study, as well. Also, it was reported that physical activity increases exhaled breath isoprene level 3-4 times [83]. However, this effect is short-term during the exercise. Thus, it was assumed that elevation in isoprene level is not a consequence of increased endogenous production, but rather due to the changes in pulmonary gas exchange during increased physical effort [83]. In the current study, we wanted to examine if there is a long-term effect on breath isoprene level in professional athletes due to their constantly high physical activity. As they were not having training on the sampling day, we did not obtain such a result, which confirms previous hypothesis.

Study weaknesses

As the instrument used in this study is portable, our goal was to conduct these pilot studies on-site, in different European cities. However, due to the COVID-19 restrictions, and the project deadlines, we were forced to ship samples for analysis. We acknowledge this as a weakness of this study. Thus, Tedlar® bags were selected as these were proven to keep our analytes of interest up to 3

days, as mentioned in the text above. As our goal was to determine the relative change in meal consumption and provide a framework for VOC concentration levels in different population groups, on-site analysis would provide similar results. Nevertheless, in our future work, we plan to conduct on-site analysis as well and be able to provide insight into the method's robustness. Furthermore, another weakness of the study may be a lot of variables involved: sampling in different countries, providing the meals that are not exactly the same, not having a dedicated control group for each examined participant category (e.g., people with diabetes versus people who do not have diabetes, with similar other characteristics). Also, an objective control of the preparation phase for the sampling (e.g., fasting, teeth brushing etc.) would be desirable. At this stage, our goal was to examine whether some correlations can be noticed among different participant groups, which could direct us into more detailed studies in the future. Also, this study can represent a pioneer work for further examination of different diet types (e.g., vegan, vegetarian) or the impact of different meal compositions (e.g., high fat, low fat, high protein, etc.), as results obtained.

Conclusions

Knowing that diet and lifestyle habits are directly related to metabolic disorders, these represent a good tackling point in getting the personalized solution for optimal nutrition and a healthy life in general. Since breath analysis is simpler than blood analysis, it could be used in the future for the analysis of large groups of people, and to provide primary selection and indicate the need for more accurate diagnostic techniques. Additionally, the novel portable and affordable instrumentation in breath analysis is welcome, enabling simpler diagnostics for the patients and the healthcare system.

This study had two goals. The first one was to confirm that recently validated MIMS instrument and method could also be employed for breath analysis in different population groups on a larger scale.. The second, and main goal, was to examine the food and lifestyle assessment on selected breath VOCs in population groups with common metabolic disorders and different lifestyle habits.

Based on the obtained concentration levels and previous findings it has been shown that portable MIMS instrument is successfully employed in this study for the determination of the exhaled breath acetone, ethanol, isoprene, and n-pentane levels. This was done for different populations: people with overweight, people with obesity, people with T2DM, people with CVD, people with a poor-quality diet, and professional athletes with samples collected before the meal and after the meal. However, it should be noted that, at this stage, this methodology cannot be used to distinguish the participants with different metabolic disorders, different diet types or different lifestyle habits. Nevertheless, all findings reported in this study are promising and may be a new starting point for future and more focused studies. In our future work, we also plan to conduct on-site analysis to be able to provide insight into the method's robustness.

Author Contributions

Milena Aleksić – Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing. **Andrea Simeon** – Software, Formal analysis, Visualization. **Djordje Vujić** –

Methodology, Visualization. **Stamatios Giannoukos** – Methodology, Writing – review, and editing. **Boris Brkić** – Supervision, Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing.

Competing interests

The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

Consent for publication

All the authors have approved the final version of the manuscript.

Compliance with ethical standards

Exhaled breath samples used in this research were collected with informed consent and ethical approvals. Participants were informed about possible publishing of the study results in the scientific purposes. In the United Kingdom, the samples were collected from people with overweight and those who had poor-quality diet. The ethical approval was obtained from University of Surry Ethical Committee on 20 May 2021 (approval ID: FHMS 20-21 131 EGA). In Greece, the samples were collected from people with overweight, people with obesity, and professional athletes with ethical approval obtained from the Research Ethics and Conduct Committee of the International Hellenic University on 20 September 2021 (approval ID: 17/20-09-2021). In Belgium, the samples were collected from people with cardiovascular disease, with ethical approval obtained from Ethics Committee Research UZ/KZ Leuven on 23 December 2021 (approval ID: S63344). In Germany, the samples were collected from people with diabetes type 2, with ethical approval obtained from Ethikkommission Charité on 26 July 2022 (approval ID: EA4/110/20). Samples were transferred to Serbia and analyzed immediately upon delivery. Research in Serbia was conducted with the ethical approval from the independent ethical advisor, Prof Gordana Vilotijević Dautović who is an expert in medical ethics and university professor in medical ethics and pediatrician pulmonology at the Medical Faculty of the University of Novi Sad. The ethical approval was obtained on 18 November 2021 (approval ID: 2021-01-3/172). Along with the samples, all participants provided data about their lifestyle by filling out a questionnaire. All samples and questionnaires were pseudo-anonymized prior transfer to Serbia. Material Transfer Agreements were signed between BioSense Institute and each institution that recruited participants, separately. The agreements regulated the collection and analysis of the samples, and the collection and processing of the data during the pilot studies. The research was done in accordance with Declaration of Helsinki, European Union and local national regulations, and European General Data Protection Regulation.

Funding

This research is part of the PROTEIN project (*Personalized nutrition for healthy living*), funded by the European Union, under the research and innovation program "Horizon 2020", under grant agreement number 817732 (<https://doi.org.10.3030/817732>). The final aim of this project was to develop a nutritional mobile application to improve the life habits of users. Also, this research study was supported by the "Horizon 2020" ANTARES project under grant agreement number 739570 (<https://doi.org.10.3030/739570>). Finally, Milena Aleksić and Andrea Simeon acknowledge the financial support of the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia (Grant No. 451-03-68/2022-14/200358).

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to acknowledge all people who were involved in the recruitment of participants in partner institutions within the PROTEIN project: Dr. Kathryn Hart, Dr. Saskia Wilson-Barnes, and Lapad Pongcharoenyong from the University of Surrey in the United Kingdom, Dr. Maria Hassapidou, Elena Patra and Anna Kokkinopoulou from the International Hellenic University in Greece, Dr. Veronique Cornelisen, and Elise from Katolische University

Leuven in Belgium, Dr. Andreas Pfeiffer, Elena Lalama and Marta Csanalosi from CHARITE in Germany. Also, we want to express gratitude to all voluntary participants involved in this study.

Safety precautions

During the sampling collection all personnel and participants were wearing the face masks as a precaution measure. Participant temporarily discarded the masks only during the sampling process and meal consumption. All personnel additionally were protected with laboratory coat and gloves. Video tutorial for handling the sampling bags was provided for participants on the sampling site, so they were able to perform the sampling by themselves, under the personnel's supervision. Sampling bags filled with samples were collected by the personnel and packed for transport. During the analysis, the analyst was protected with face mask, laboratory coat and gloves. Sampling bags were always firstly connected to the inlet probe of the instrument, and then the valve of the bag was opened. Thus, the breath sample was never released in the environment. The whole amount of samples was used. Used empty sampling bags were disposed to communal waste, according to the manufacturer recommendation.

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